

Fragmentation of 1,6-Bis(arylsulphinyl)hexa-2,4-diyne, 1-Arylsulphenyl-6-arylsulphinylhexa-2,4-diyne and 1-Arylsulphinyl-6-arylsulphonylhexa-2,4-diyne under Electron Impact

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Manuscript received 3 February 1986, revised 1 September 1986, accepted 13 November 1986

The mass spectral rearrangement of 1,6-bis(arylsulphinyl)hexa-2,4-diyne (3), 1-arylsulphenyl-6-arylsulphinylhexa-2,4-diyne (4) and 1-arylsulphinyl-6-arylsulphonylhexa-2,4-diyne (5) were studied. While 4 showed loss of oxygen and hexadiynyl moiety, 3 extruded hexadiynyl moiety and oxygen and 5 showed extrusion of sulphur dioxide in one mode, loss of oxygen and hexadiynyl moiety on the other.

STUDIES reported by Thyagarajan *et al*¹ illustrates that 1,6-bis(arylthio)-2,4-hexadiynes (1) extruded hexadiynyl moiety and the oxidised molecule 1,6-bis(arylsulphonyl)-2,4-hexadiynes (2) loose SO₂ and even two SO₂ units under electron impact. In between these bis-sulphides (1) and bis-sulphones (2) there exists three different types of partially oxidised compounds, viz. 1,6-bis(arylsulphinyl)-2,4-hexadiynes (3), 1-arylsulphenyl-6-arylsulphinyl-2,4-hexadiynes (4) and 1-arylsulphinyl-6-arylsulphonyl-2,4-hexadiynes (5). We have recently reported² the synthesis of these compounds (3-5) and have undertaken the study of the fragmentation behaviour of these compounds under electron impact to seek further supportive evidence for this feature^{1,3-5} or reveal any variation in the mode of fragmentation.

3-5 a; Ar = *p*-methylphenyl
b; Ar = phenyl
c; Ar = *p*-chlorophenyl

Mass spectra of the bis-sulphoxide (3): All the bis-sulphoxides showed strong peaks for fragments from the scission of C-C bond between two propynyl units, sulphoxide to sulphenate rearrangements (with aryl and alkyl migration), cleavage of aryl sulphur and alkyl sulphur bond *etc.* These compounds do not show any loss of SO from the molecular ion which is a commonly predictable mode of fragmentation^{6,7} but show loss of oxygen⁸.

These bis-sulphoxides show remarkable loss of hexadiynyl moiety from the parent molecular ion. This observation is somewhat similar to that of Thyagarajan *et al.* in case of bis-sulphides¹ 3a shows loss of 2H and 2H consecutively (Chart 1).

* Also showed *m/z* for all the fragments corresponding to Cl³⁷.

Chart 1

Mass spectra of 1-arylsulphenyl-6-arylsulphinylhexa-2,4-diyne (4): These compounds do not show any initial loss of C₆H₄ unit or SO from the molecular ion, but show loss of oxygen⁸ and loss of hexadiynyl moiety. This loss of oxygen and hexadiynyl moiety may proceed through either a sequential process or a concerted process. In another mode these compounds show initial loss of 2H and

ment from alkyl-S bond cleavage, sulphone sulphinate rearrangement *etc.* Representative spectra of 3-5 are depicted in Figs. 1-3.

Fig. 3

This study clearly shows that the bis-sulphoxides (3) eliminate hexadiynyl moiety just like the bis-sulphides (1), the sulphide-sulphoxide system (4) loses oxygen and hexadiynyl moiety whereas the sulphoxide-sulphone system (5) loses one oxygen and hexadiynyl moiety under electron impact. So it may be concluded that under electron impact,

hexadiynyl moiety is eliminated only from bis-sulphides (1) or from bis-sulphoxides (3) among the type of compounds (1-5) studied so far.

Experimental

Low resolution mass spectra were secured on a Varian M-77 instrument at electron energies of 70 and 20 eV using PFK as mass standard. It was found that variation of sample temperature had very little effect on the spectra. Compounds 3-5 were prepared according to our earlier published procedure².

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Dr. D. K. Bates and R. Thomas Winters, Michigan Technological University, U.S.A., for securing mass spectra and also for helpful comments, Professor J. W. Lown, University of Alberta, Canada for mass spectra of compounds, the C.S.I.R., New Delhi and University of Kalyani, for financial assistance.

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